

HumiShade Umbrella

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Abstract: The HumiShade Umbrella presents an innovative solution to the challenges posed by hot and dry climates combining the functionality of a traditional umbrella with a built-in humidifier. This product not only provides protection from the sun but also enhances comfort and health in dry environments with the needs of users. This umbrella also alleviates discomfort associated with low moisture levels, such as dry skin and dehydration. By utilising solar power for sustainable energy, the HumiShade offers portability and convenience, making it ideal for on-the-go use. HumiShade aims to revolutionize the way people interact with their environment by offering a practical and comfortable solution for users worldwide. It focuses on reducing UltraViolet (UV) exposure, enhancing user experience, and driving economic opportunities through sustainable design.

Keywords: umbrella; humidifier; sun; low moisture levels; portability; reducing UV exposure

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1. INTRODUCTION

HumiShade Umbrella is a shade solution from hot weather to enhance user comfort when outside, especially when walking. It helps provide users with enhanced sun protection and cooling capabilities, ensuring users can enjoy their outdoor activities without worrying about sunburn or overheating. With the HumiShade Umbrella, users can effectively manage their time outside by staying comfortably shaded where it allows them to maximise their enjoyment without the need for frequent breaks or concerns about sun exposure. Users can gain a lot of benefit by using the HumiShade Umbrella as it provides comfort to users' needs. This umbrella with a humidifier is specially designed to meet the user's requirements in battling heat and humidity in the tropics. This innovative product is not just any common umbrella, but also a tool that can allow users to stay under hot days for a longer time.

2. OBJECTIVE

1. The main objective of HumiShade Umbrella is to reduce UltraViolet (UV) exposure.
 2. HumiShade aims to create an umbrella that seamlessly integrates functionality with design that complements Malaysian fashion sensibilities.
 3. The last objective is to drive economic opportunity through sustainable design and innovation.
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3. NOVELTY AND THE UNIQUENESS OF THE PRODUCT

The HumiShade Umbrella is a product designed to help users manage hot weather conditions. The HumiShade Umbrella is the combination of two tools, an umbrella and a humidifier, and the combination of these tools provides numerous benefits to users, making this product unique. In this product, solar power is applied so that users do not need to recharge the umbrella multiple times. By using solar panels, it can charge the battery of the humidifier, and at the same time, the use of solar panels is a great way to utilise clean, renewable energy for environmental sustainability. This type of umbrella can help users stay under the sun for longer periods because it protects them from hot weather and reduces discomfort in dry environments. These features are very suitable and useful for tourists, especially when they travel to tropical countries, as they often walk more frequently and stand under the sun for longer periods.

4. DISCUSSION

HumiShade tackles the challenges of hot climate with a groundbreaking umbrella design. It transcends the limitations of traditional umbrellas by incorporating a built-in humidifier that offers superior protection and comfort under the scorching sun. This innovative feature goes beyond mere shade. The integrated humidifier generates a fine mist that cools users through a process called evaporative cooling (Kapilan et al., 2023). As the mist absorbs heat from the surrounding air, it creates a refreshing sensation and eliminates the need for frequent recharging. HumiShade’s design prioritises sustainability as well. Solar panels power the humidifier that controls the sun’s energy to minimise environmental impact (Alnaimat et al., 2021). Furthermore, HumiShade transcends functionality with stylish design that seamlessly complements modern aesthetics and encourages regular use. By prioritising both protection and comfort, HumiShade empowers Malaysians to navigate their sunny climate with confidence and promotes sun safety and environmental responsibility.

Table 1. Method of Using HumiShade Umbrella

<p>Step 1- Open the umbrella from its packaging. To open the umbrella, hold it upright and press the designated button or manually slide the mechanism to extend the canopy. The material of this umbrella is fabric nylon.</p>	
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Use a solar panel to charge the battery of the Humidifier. The solar will be at the top. This is because the tropics receive more direct sunlight. In addition, the direction of the sun's rays will change according to the month. The solar panel that will be used is The PowerFilm LightSaver USB solar panel. This solar panel will charge the battery using USB. The PowerFilm LightSaver USB solar panel can be used even when the sun isn't shining. The weight of this solar panel is 4.9 oz (ounce) equivalent 138.913 grams and the size is 7.8 X 1.6. In addition, this type of solar panel can be folded according to the folding state of the umbrella because of its material which can be folded in any condition. Make sure the battery level is full.

Examine the state of the water. To get moist air, add water to the humidifier. Ensure that the water level is at its maximum. A humidifier must have the right amount of water to function properly. This will guarantee a constant output of mist. Fill the water by turning the handle

Step 2- To turn on, press the on button. When the button is pressed, high-frequency sound vibration is used to break up the water into droplets, which are then released into the air to create a cool mist humidifier. The mist will come out of the top of the canopy. We refer to this technique as the Ultrasonic method. This humidifier can work in an open area (Reed, 2023). When the mist is generated on the handle, it will directly hit the user's face area. This is because the curved umbrella can prevent the mist from coming out of the umbrella when it comes into direct contact, it can cause

<p>breathing problems. Using too much moisture in the air can also worsen flu symptoms. This is why this innovation strategically emits mist from the top of the umbrella (canopy) to avoid directly misting the user's face and to maintain user comfort during operation.</p>	
<p>Step 3- Press the off button to turn it off. After using it, press the turn off button. Make sure there is enough pressure to turn the button off. Confirm the umbrella is closed securely to ensure that it is safe to keep the water moist or completely off.</p>	<p>The diagram illustrates the operation of the HumiShade Umbrella. The top part shows the umbrella open with mist being emitted from the canopy, and an arrow pointing to a button on the handle. The bottom part shows the umbrella in three stages: fully open, partially closed, and fully closed.</p>

5. CONCLUSION

The HumiShade Umbrella emerges as a significant innovation in the realm of personal sun protection. Its unique misting technology transcends the limitations of traditional sun protection that transform walks under a scorching sun into comfortable outings. This innovative product goes beyond basic shade that can offer cooling through its misting function. With HumiShade, users can conquer the outdoors with confidence where they can maximise their enjoyment without succumbing to sunburn or overheating.

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